

Concept for Planning Sustainable Factories

Authors : T. Mersmann, P. Nyhuis

Abstract : In the current economic climate, for many businesses it is generally no longer sufficient to pursue exclusively economic interests. Instead, integrating ecological and social goals into the corporate targets is becoming ever more important. However, the holistic integration of these new goals is missing from current factory planning approaches. This article describes the conceptual framework for a planning methodology for sustainable factories. To this end, the description of the key areas for action is followed by a description of the principal components for the systematization of sustainability for factories and their stakeholders. Finally, a conceptual framework is presented which integrates the components formulated into an established factory planning procedure.

Keywords : factory planning, stakeholder, systematization, sustainability

Conference Title : ICPME 2014 : International Conference on Production and Manufacturing Engineering

Conference Location : Tokyo, Japan

Conference Dates : May 29-30, 2014